

Hansch analysis of antitumor 4 β -(arylamino)-4-desoxypodophyllotoxins and their 4'-demethyl analogs

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Antitumor activities (*in vitro* KB cell cytotoxicity and cellular protein-linked DNA damage data) of 4-arylamino derivatives (P1-P16) of epipodophyllotoxin and 4'-demethylepipodophyllotoxin are subjected to Hansch analysis with various physicochemical parameters [electronic (σ), hydrophobicity (π) and steric (MR)] of the phenyl ring substituents (R_1) alongwith some indicator variables. The best relation [EV = 75.9%, $R = 0.898$, $F = 16.7$ (df = 3, 12), PRESS : $r = 0.808$] relating KB cell cytotoxicity data with physicochemical/indicator parameters suggests that bulkier substituents at *ortho* and *meta* positions on the phenyl ring reduce the activity while an electron-withdrawing *para*-substituent increases the activity. Further, 4'-demethylation does not alter the activity significantly. The best relation [EV = 84.6%, $R = 0.936$, $F = 28.4$ (df = 3, 12), PRESS : $r = 0.890$] involving cellular protein-DNA complex formation data shows that 4'-demethyl derivatives have higher activity. The equation also suggests that size of *ortho*-substituent and lipophilicity of *meta* and *para* substituents (R_1) on the phenyl ring have negative contributions. Poor correlation ($r = 0.396$) is found between the two types of activity data. The hypothesis that DNA-breakage is insufficient to cause cell death may explain the lack of correlation between the activity parameters.

The rich chemical diversity of natural products, which once served as the only source of medicine for mankind, continues to be utilized as important source of lead compounds for the present medicinal chemistry programs¹. Various natural product constituents have been target of modifications for design and synthesis of newer drug candidates with better therapeutic efficacy. Podophyllotoxins are amongst the examples of natural product derived drugs.

Podophyllotoxin is a cytotoxic drug isolated from the root of May apple tree. *Podophyllum peltatum* (American mandrake) and *P. emodi* are respectively American and Himalayan plants that are in use as cathartics in folk medicine in the respective places^{2,3}. There are records of topical applications of alcoholic extract known as podophyllin in the treatment of cancer from the nineteenth century¹. The first chemical constituent isolated from podophyllin was podophyllotoxin (1). It was found that sugar derivatives of podophyllotoxin (lignan glycosides) are having less anticancer activity as well as less toxicity⁴. It was further found that 1-*epi* analogs of podophyllotoxin and its sugar derivatives are more potent compounds¹. Two semisynthetic glycoside derivatives (with 1 β -configuration), teniposide (2) and etoposide (3), have been developed that show significant therapeutic activity in

several human neoplasms including pediatric leukemia, small cell carcinoma of the lung, testicular tumors, Hodgkin's disease and large cell lymphomas^{5,6}. Though

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Table 1. Antitumor activities of 4-arylaminoepidophyllotoxins

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	KB cell cytotoxicity				Cellular protein-DNA complex formation					
			IC ₅₀ μM	pC			BA (%)*	log BA				
				Obs.	Calc	Res.		Pres.	Obs	Calc	Res.	Pres
P1	<i>o</i> -OH	CH ₃	4.11	2.386	2.453	-0.067	-0.101	6	0.778	0.902	-0.124	-0.224
P2	<i>m</i> -OH	CH ₃	0.31	3.509	3.220	0.289	0.315	37	1.568	1.383	0.185	0.290
P3	<i>p</i> -OH	CH ₃	0.59	3.229	2.980	0.249	0.430	21	1.322	1.383	-0.061	-0.096
P4	<i>o</i> -OH	H	4.54	2.343	2.453	-0.110	-0.166	151	2.179	1.970	0.209	0.246
P5	<i>m</i> -OH	H	0.45	3.347	3.220	0.127	0.138	290	2.462	2.451	0.011	0.015
P6	<i>p</i> -OH	H	2.26	2.646	2.980	-0.334	-0.577	211	2.324	2.451	-0.127	-0.185
P7	<i>o</i> -F	H	0.25	3.602	3.413	0.189	0.209	121	2.083	2.232	-0.149	-0.168
P8	<i>m</i> -F	H	0.23	3.638	3.425	0.213	0.237	158	2.199	2.168	0.031	0.034
P9	<i>p</i> -F	H	0.24	3.620	3.483	0.137	0.153	213	2.328	2.168	0.160	0.176
P10	<i>m,m'</i> -(Cl) ₂	H	1.08	2.967	3.436	-0.469	-0.525	115	2.061	2.119	-0.058	-0.064
P11	<i>o</i> -Cl	H	2.34	2.631	2.453	0.178	0.266	32	1.505	1.539	-0.034	-0.192
P12	<i>m</i> -Cl	H	2.29	2.640	2.882	-0.242	-0.332	51	1.708	1.969	-0.261	-0.300
P13	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	0.22	3.658	3.685	-0.027	-0.036	99	1.996	1.969	0.027	0.031
P14	<i>m</i> -Br	H	2.36	2.627	2.580	0.047	0.145	62	1.792	1.916	-0.124	-0.149
P15	<i>p</i> -Br	H	0.22	3.658	3.682	-0.024	-0.031	179	2.253	1.916	0.337	0.404
P16	<i>p</i> -I	H	0.34	3.469	3.624	-0.155	-0.188	64	1.806	1.826	-0.020	-0.026

pC = $-\log IC_{50}$ (mM); *Equimolar response at $IC_{50} = 10 \mu M$

Obs = Observed activity; Calc. = calculated activity, Res. = observed - calculated; Pres. = predicted residual (from PRESS equations)

Eqns. 3 and 6 have been used to calculate KB cell cytotoxicity (pC) and protein linked DNA damage (log BA) respectively and corresponding Pres values are shown.

podophyllotoxin acts as spindle poison that inhibits cell proliferation by binding to tubulin and preventing formation of microtubules, etoposide and teniposide have no effect on microtubular structures^{1,7}. These can induce strand-breaks in DNA, which is probably mediated by interactions with topoisomerase II⁸.

Lee *et al.*⁹ reported that substitution of glycosidic moiety of etoposide by an 4-alkylamino side-chain also retains inhibitory activity on human DNA topoisomerase II as well as cellular protein-linked DNA breakage activity. The same group of authors further reported¹⁰ some novel antitumor 4-arylamino derivatives of epidophyllotoxin having DNA strand breaking activity which is due to inhibition of DNA topoisomerase II.

The present communication is a Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship (QSAR) study (Hansch model) of antitumor activities of 4-arylamino derivatives (P1-P16) of epidophyllotoxin and 4'-demethylepidophyllotoxin reported by Lee *et al.* with different physicochemical parameters of the substituents. The compounds possess two regions of structural variations, one being the 4-arylamino moiety differing in phenyl ring substitution (R₁) pattern and the other being the R₂ segment (presence or absence of methyl group). Two sets of activity data, *in vitro* KB cell cytotoxicity (pC) and cellular protein-DNA complex formation (log BA), have been used for the QSAR analyses. The nature of structural variations and biological activity data are listed in Table 1. The physicochemical

parameters [electronic (σ), hydrophobicity (π) and steric (molar refractivity, MR)] for the phenyl ring substituents are taken from literature¹¹ and listed in Table 2. Though only halogen and hydroxy substituents (R₁) are present on the phenyl ring, an inspection of Table 2 suggests that the values of the physicochemical parameters are distributed in a considerably wide range values (π values range from -0.67 to 1.12, σ_m and σ_p range from 0 to 0.39 and from -0.37 to 0.23, respectively, and MR values range from 0.092 to 1.394). Thus, it was thought that Hansch analysis^{12,13} could be undertaken for the antitumor activities of the compounds to derive an insight into the substitutional requirements for better activity and also to develop equations having predictive capacity, which may be used to calculate theoretically the activities also for such compounds having substituents that may be absent in the present data set.

Table 2. Physicochemical parameters of the aromatic substituents (R₁)^a

R ₁	π	σ_m^a	σ_p^a	MR ^b
F	0.14	0.34	0.06	0.092
Cl	0.71	0.37	0.23	0.603
Br	0.86	0.39	0.23	0.888
I	1.12	0.35	0.18	1.394
OH	-0.67	0.12	-0.37	0.285
H	0	0	0	0.103

^aTaken from Ref. 11 ^a*meta* or *para* with respect to amino moiety ^bMR values are scaled by a factor of 0.1 as usual.

The sum of the values of a physicochemical parameter

Table 3. Summary of PRESS equations

Model equation : $Y = \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \alpha$

Key equation no.	Y	x ₁	x ₂	x ₃	Average* regression constants (standard deviations)				PRESS statistics	
					β_1 (sd)	β_2 (sd)	β_3 (sd)	α (sd)	r (EV%)	AVRES (SEE)
3	pC	I _o	MR _m	σ_p	-0.960 (0.038)	-1.066 (0.071)	1.168 (0.165)	3.633 (0.036)	0.808 (65.2)	0.241 (0.296)
6	log BA	MR _o	I _{R2}	π_{m+p}	-1.338 (0.096)	-1.069 (0.037)	-0.350 (0.023)	2.493 (0.027)	0.890 (79.3)	0.163 (0.202)
12	log [BA × (IC ₅₀) ^β]	MR _o	I _{R2}	π_{m+p}	-0.967 (0.235)	-1.057 (0.029)	-0.351 (0.016)	1.843 (0.050)	0.860 (73.9)	0.149 (0.213)

* n = 16.

Note: The regression constants of each term of the PRESS equations obtained by omission of different single compounds do not differ significantly except in the following cases:

(A) Key equation 3; (i) PRESS eq. omitting compd. P3 : $\beta_3 = 1.549$; (ii) PRESS eq. omitting compd. P6 : $\beta_3 = 0.662$, (B) Key equation 6 : PRESS eq. omitting compd. P11 : $\beta_1 = -1.040$, (C) Key equation 12 : PRESS eq. omitting compd. P11 : $\beta_1 = -0.107$.

for the groups (substituents) present at two *ortho/meta*-positions were taken as the corresponding parameter for the *ortho/meta*-substituents, e.g. MR_o for compound P1 is MR(OH) + MR(H) = 0.285 + 0.103 = 0.388. The multiple regression analyses were done using a program RRR98¹⁴ developed by one of the authors. The quality of the regression equations¹⁵ was judged by examining the parameters like explained variance (EV%), coefficient of variation (CV%), correlation coefficient (r or R), standard error of estimate (SEE), variance ratio (F) with degree of freedom (df), average of absolute values of residuals (AVRES) and 95% confidence intervals of the regression constants. Autocorrelation among the predictor variables in a multivariate equation was also checked. All the accepted equations have regression constants and variance ratio significant at 95 and 99% levels, respectively, if not stated otherwise (regression constants that are significant at 90% level/below 90% level are superscripted with */# and F values insignificant at 95% level are marked with +). A compound was considered as an outlier for an equation when residual (absolute difference between calculated and observed activity) was more than twice the SEE of that equation. The predictive feature and robustness of the equations were tested from PRESS statistics obtained by running programs¹⁴ KRPRES1 and KRPRES2 using 'leave-one-out' technique.

Results and Discussion

An indicator parameter I_o denoting presence (value 1) or absence (value 0) of an *ortho*-substituent on the phenyl ring having larger size than that of hydrogen could singularly explain 39.9% of the variance of the KB cell

cytotoxicity data,

$$pC = -0.824 (\pm 0.534) I_o + 3.278 (\pm 0.231) \quad (1)$$

$$EV = 39.9\%, CV = 12.4\%, r = 0.663, SEE = 0.388, F = 11.0 (df = 1, 14), AVRES = 0.307, n = 16.$$

The 95% confidence intervals of the regression constants are given in parentheses.

When MR value of the *meta*-substituent (MR_m) was included in the above equation, the explained variance rose by 20 units and F ratio increased by 1 unit. However, compound P6 behaves as an outlier,

$$pC = -0.955 (\pm 0.448) I_o - 1.055 (\pm 0.797) MR_m + 3.626 (\pm 0.324) \quad (2)$$

$$EV = 60.3\%, CV = 10.1\%, R = 0.810, SEE = 0.316, F = 12.4 (df = 2, 13), AVRES = 0.228, n = 16.$$

Another parameter σ_p (Hammett σ parameter for *para*-substituent) was included in eqn. (2) to obtain the following equation explaining 75.9% variation of the activity and without having any outlier,

$$pC = -0.960 (\pm 0.352) I_o - 1.061 (\pm 0.627) MR_m + 1.170 (\pm 0.833) \sigma_p + 3.632 (\pm 0.244) \quad (3)$$

$$EV = 75.9\%, CV = 7.9\%, R = 0.898, SEE = 0.246, F = 16.7 (df = 3, 12), AVRES = 0.179, n = 16.$$

A large number of various other combinations of parameters representing electronic, hydrophobicity and steric parameters of the phenyl ring substituents were attempted, but none was found to be statistically superior to eqn. (3). The R₂ segment did not show significant contribution to the activity. The autocorrelation (r) matrix for the eqn. (3) is I_o vs MR_m/ σ_p = 0.221/0.007; MR_m vs σ_p =

0.006. Thus, the predictor variables are mutually orthogonal to each other. The PRESS statistics of eqn. (3) is : $r = 0.808$, $SEE = 0.296$, $AVRES = 0.241$. The regression constants of each term of the PRESS equations obtained by omission of different single compounds do not differ significantly (Table 3).

The above equations suggest that an *ortho*-substituent having larger size than that of hydrogen on the phenyl ring reduces the activity (pC) expectedly due to steric reason. The MR value of the *meta*-substituent on the phenyl ring has a negative contribution; thus bulkier group at the *meta*-position is not preferred. The size of the *meta*-substituent may play a critical role for the proper orientation of the phenyl ring that may interact with the receptive site and other parts of the drug molecule. The positive regression coefficient of σ_p suggests that an electron-withdrawing *para*-substituent is conducive to the activity (pC). The absence of R_2 term in the equation implies that 4'-demethylation does not significantly alter the activity (pC).

While deriving equations involving cellular protein-DNA complex formation (log BA) data, the R_2 segment was found to contribute significantly. A dummy parameter I_{R_2} indicating presence or absence of the methyl group (with values 1 and 0 respectively) could singularly explain 53.9% of the variance,

$$\log BA = -0.831 (\pm 0.414) I_{R_2} + 2.054 (\pm 0.179) \quad (4)$$

EV = 53.9%, CV = 15.9%, $r = 0.755$, $SEE = 0.302$, $F = 18.5$ (df = 1, 14), $AVRES = 0.238$, $n = 16$.

Inclusion of molar refractivity parameter of *ortho*-substituent (R_1) increased the explained variance by 12 units though variance ratio reduced by 3 units,

$$\log BA = -0.820 (\pm 0.357) I_{R_2} - 1.229 (\pm 1.070) MR_o + 2.370 (\pm 0.316) \quad (5)$$

EV = 66.3%, CV = 13.6%, $R = 0.841$, $SEE = 0.258$, $F = 15.7$ (df = 2, 13), $AVRES = 0.196$, $n = 16$.

A third parameter π_{m+p} (sum of hydrophobicity of *meta* and *para* substituents) increased statistical quality of eqn. (5) to a great extent,

$$\log BA = -1.068 (\pm 0.278) I_{R_2} - 1.356 (\pm 0.733) MR_o - 0.350 (\pm 0.188) \pi_{m+p} + 2.496 (\pm 0.223) \quad (6)$$

EV = 84.6%, CV = 9.2%, $R = 0.936$, $SEE = 0.174$, $F = 28.4$ (df = 3, 12), $AVRES = 0.120$, $n = 16$.

Eqn. (6) does not have any outlier. The autocorrelation (r) matrix is I_{R_2} vs MR_o / $\pi_{m+p} = 0.027/0.481$; MR_o vs $\pi_{m+p} = 0.095$. The PRESS statistics is : $r = 0.890$, $SEE = 0.202$, $AVRES = 0.163$. The regression constants of each term of different PRESS equations do not differ significantly (Table 3).

Though various other combinations of the physico-chemical parameters were attempted, eqn. (6) was found to be of the best statistical quality explaining protein-DNA complex formation data. The negative regression coefficient of I_{R_2} in eqn. (6) suggests that the 4'-demethyl analogs have higher activity (log BA). Further, the negative coefficients of MR_o and π_{m+p} indicate that size of *ortho*-substituent and lipophilicity of the *meta*- and *para*-substituents have negative impact on the protein linked DNA damage activity.

The two kinds of activities (KB cell cytotoxicity data and cellular protein-DNA complex formation) were found to be poorly correlated,

$$\log BA = 0.351 (\pm 0.466)^{\#} pC + 0.803 (\pm 1.474)^{\#} \quad (7)$$

EV = 9.6%, CV = 22.2%, $r = 0.396$, $SEE = 0.422$, $F = 2.6^+$ (df = 1, 14), $AVRES = 0.310$, $n = 16$.

The regression constants and F value of the above equation are insignificant at 95% level and compound P1 behaves as an outlier. It was previously suggested that DNA-break might be insufficient to cause cell death¹⁶ and this explains lack of correlation between these activity parameters.

When another predictor variable I_{R_2} was introduced in eqn. (7), statistical quality rose significantly.

$$\log BA = 0.298 (\pm 0.300)^* pC - 0.801 (\pm 0.373) I_{R_2} + 1.116 (\pm 0.443) \quad (8)$$

EV = 63.3%, CV = 14.2%, $R = 0.826$, $SEE = 0.269$, $F = 13.9$ (df = 2, 13), $AVRES = 0.202$, $n = 16$.

Eqn. (8) is without any outlier. The regression coefficient of pC is significant at 90% level. The autocorrelation (r) between I_{R_2} and pC is 0.081. Eqn. (8) suggests that for the protein-linked DNA damage R_2 segment plays significant role while for KB cell cytotoxicity R_2 segment is of less importance.

Eqn. (8) could be improved further by introduction of the term π_{m+p} ,

$$\log BA = 0.318 (\pm 0.226) pC - 1.038 (\pm 0.319) I_{R_2} - 0.334 (\pm 0.215) \pi_{m+p} + 1.144 (\pm 0.715) \quad (9)$$

EV = 80.0%, CV = 10.5%, $R = 0.915$, $SEE = 0.200$, $F = 20.6$ (df = 3, 12), $AVRES = 0.130$, $n = 16$.

Compound P11 behaves as an outlier. The autocorrelation (r) between pC and π_{m+p} is 0.088. On removal of compound P11, an equation with excellent statistical quality was obtained,

$$\log BA = 0.243 (\pm 0.164) pC - 1.112 (\pm 0.227) I_{R_2} - 0.367 (\pm 0.152) \pi_{m+p} + 1.433 (\pm 0.525) \quad (10)$$

EV = 90.4%, CV = 7.2%, $R = 0.961$, $SEE = 0.138$, $F = 44.8$ (df = 3, 11), $AVRES = 0.093$, $n = 15$.

The autocorrelation (r) matrix for eqn. (10) is pC vs $I_{R2}/\pi_{m+p} = 0.118/0.075$; I_{R2} vs $\pi_{m+p} = 0.493$.

When another predictor variable MR_o was introduced in eqn. (9), the following equation without having any outlier was derived,

$$\log BA = 0.177 (\pm 0.212) pC - 1.055 (\pm 0.257) I_{R2} - 0.351 (\pm 0.173) \pi_{m+p} - 1.013 (\pm 0.792) MR_o + 1.853 (\pm 0.705) \quad (11)$$

EV = 87.1%, CV = 8.4%, $R = 0.952$, SEE = 0.159, $F = 26.4$ (df = 4, 11), AVRES = 0.098, $n = 16$.

The autocorrelation (r) between pC and MR_o is 0.522. The regression coefficient of pC in eqn. (11) is significant at 90% level. However, a sixteen-membered dataset ($n = 16$) is not amenable to multiple regression with four predictor variables. To avoid this problem, the variable pC was taken to the left-hand-side of the equation and multiple regression of the new response variable $\log [BA \times (IC_{50})^\beta]$ with the predictor variables I_{R2} , π_{m+p} and MR_o was carried out. The value of β is same as the regression coefficient of pC in eqn. (11),

$$\log [BA \times (IC_{50})^\beta] = -1.055 (\pm 0.243) I_{R2} - 0.351 (\pm 0.164) \pi_{m+p} - 1.013 (\pm 0.642) MR_o + 1.853 (\pm 0.195) \quad (12)$$

EV = 86.6%, CV = 11.3%, $R = 0.945$, SEE = 0.153, $F = 33.3$ (df = 3, 12), AVRES = 0.098, $n = 16$.

Eqn. (12) is of excellent statistical quality and may be used for computing one activity data when the other is known. The PRESS statistics of the equation is : $r = 0.860$, SEE = 0.213, AVRES = 0.149 (Table 3).

The above QSAR studies throws some light on the substitutional requirements of antitumor 4 β -(arylamino)-4-desoxydophyllotoxins and their 4'-demethyl analogs. However, considering less number of data points and lack of diversity in the substitution pattern, more compounds need be incorporated in the data set for further extensive QSAR analysis to derive robust equations for such compounds.

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